

Single Equilibration in Classical Statistical versus Double in Quantum Mechanics

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We argue that classical statistical mechanics (say of an ideal gas) is based on a single equilibration scheme characterized by a temperature T (even in the presence of a potential $V(x)$). This single scheme is based on the maximization of entropy (subject to an average energy constraint) in order to determine probabilities for p, v and x .

Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, is based on two equilibration schemes, we argue. The first is due to a built-in probability of $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle. In this case, a potential $V(x)$ interacts with momentum (impulse hits) to create a potential energy. No velocity appears in the creation of potential energy, but does appear in the creation of average kinetic energy. Like with a classical mechanical bound state, energy becomes a system variable. This is the first equilibration. We argue that it should have its own entropy. The probability form $\exp(ipx)$ together with conservation of energy and boundary conditions fix allowable single particle energy values (which are discrete) unlike in the classical statistical mechanical case. The second equilibration occurs if there exists a mechanism for moving from one discrete E to another, e.g. photon emission/absorption. This equilibration is based on maximization of entropy (a second entropy), but the effects of the first equilibration remain because it is this first scheme which controls allowable E values. We also argue that $\exp(-iEt)$ from the first equilibration scheme may affect the usual entropy based on $\exp(-E/T)$ used in the second scheme.

Classical Statistical Mechanical Gas and Single Equilibration

A classical statistical mechanical gas (Maxwell-Boltzmann gas) is characterized by one parameter T , temperature. This parameter is proportional to the system energy and pressure, but at the same time to the average single particle kinetic energy. It governs its probability $\exp(-(\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x))/T)$. In other words, single particles may have any kinetic energy. Collisions occur at each x point so that entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ is maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ where $e_i = \frac{p^2}{2m}$ (nonrelativistically). This creates a pressure which balances the force $= -dV/dx$ with particle number at x (in a little box of size dx) being an adjustable physical parameter. In short, there is one equilibration scheme based on the maximization of entropy.

Quantum Mechanics

Time and space are often considered on the same footing if one uses ct and x . For the quantum free photon wavefunction, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, this symmetry is evident because $E=pc$ i.e.

Photon: $\exp(-i p ct + i px)$ ((1))

Thus a photon seems to have the same intrinsic probability scheme (and built-in entropy) in time and space.

This symmetry, however, is broken for a particle with mass i.e.

$$\text{Particle with rest mass: } \exp(-iEt+ipx) = \exp(-i \frac{m_0 c}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} ct + i \frac{m_0 v}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} x) \quad ((2))$$

As a result, there seems to be two different built-in entropy schemes, one for time and the other for space. This already points to two kinds of equilibrations. Here we call a built-in entropy scheme, one based on Shannon's entropy using:

$$\text{Probability} = C |\cos(px)| \text{ or } C^2 |\cos(Et)| \quad ((3))$$

$\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ both suggest two dimensional probability schemes in t and x , but one must be careful as to ascertaining a meaning for t . We have argued in previous notes that t and x are considered to be independent, but with $v=x/t$ on average. Here, we argue that t is associated with a system variable E , while p is linked with the first scheme of equilibration for a bound quantum system.

First Equilibration for a Quantum Bound State

Unlike classical statistical mechanical equilibration which is based on maximization of entropy subject to a special constraint, quantum single particle bound state statistical mechanics is based on the built-in quantum probability $\exp(ipx)$. This probability describes the effects of impulse interactions with $V(x)$, a potential, we argue. The interaction $V(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, creates a kind of potential energy term which must be added to a kind of kinetic energy term:

$$KE(x)W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \frac{1}{2} v^2 \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

Velocity v appears explicitly in ((4)) although it is usually written as p/m . Like a classical statistical mechanical gas or a classical bound system, one needs a system variable to describe equilibrium. For both the classical and quantum bound systems, this system variable is total energy, which is constant at all x points. This describes then a system in equilibrium so to speak as the entire system is characterized by E (total energy) which does not change in time. For a classical gas, T is the system parameter and it is directly linked not to total energy, but to average kinetic energy.

The first equilibration in quantum mechanics, which relies on $\exp(ipx)$, conservation of energy and boundary conditions, dictates allowable values of E total which are discrete. These have nothing to do with maximization of entropy, yet this first scheme is probabilistic or statistical.

Given that E represents the quantum system bound variable, one has the factor $\exp(-iEt)$ which describes a probability scheme associated with this system variable which differs from the probability scheme associated with $\exp(ipx)$. For example, in the literature one sees Shannon's entropies created from the probabilities $W(x)W(x)$ or $a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We have suggested adding these two entropies. $\exp(-iEt)$, however, suggests a completely different time based entropy which relies on the system variable E (total energy of

the quantum single particle bound state). This entropy is not that same as the spatial-momentum ones.

In fact, it seems that one may have two completely different potentials which yield the same ground state energy. For example, the ground state energy of a particle in a box with the infinite potential walls is: $(1/2m) (\hbar^2 \pi^2/L^2)$. The ground state of an oscillator is $\hbar \sqrt{k/m} / 2$. Equating the two by choosing L and k in a certain way yields the same system variable i.e. ground state energy. Thus both of these ground state systems have the same temporal built-in entropies based on a probability $C |\cos(Et)|$, but are physically completely different and have different spatial and momentum entropies.

As a result, one sees an asymmetry between t and x in single particle bound state quantum mechanics. Time is linked to a system variable, whereas x is related to the single particle statistical mechanics. In classical statistical mechanics, one does not have this dichotomy even though density changes in x and there is no change in time. Density in the classical statistical case is based on the number of particles at x . The dynamics of the particles is fixed by T temperature. In quantum mechanics, the dynamics of a single particle is fixed by the built-in probability $\exp(ipx)$, conservation of energy and boundary conditions.

Second Equilibration for a Quantum Single Particle Bound State

Given a set of discrete E_i (total energies) for a quantum single particle bound state, one may create a second equilibration based on the classical statistical mechanical approach of maximization of energy subject to average total energy. In such a case, the familiar MB factors $\exp(-E_i/T)$ appear together with T temperature. E_i , here, however, is not kinetic energy, but rather total energy fixed by the first equilibration scheme. Thus the first equilibration scheme has an effect on the second as it determines which E values are allowed. This in turn affects the form of common statistical variables such as second equilibration entropy. (One may note that in the case of temperature dependent Hartree-Fock, the potential $V(x)$ is created through interactions of a single particle with other particles (say in a nucleus). Thus T temperature appears in the first equilibration approach, but entropy is not maximized i.e. a Schrodinger equation (containing T) still exists. (Entropy is only maximized in the sense that it controls the weights of E_i values.)

Double Equilibration - Double Entropy?

We argue that given a double scheme of equilibration, one might need to have two entropies, one for each scheme. The usual Shannon's entropy for the MB factor $\exp(-E/T)$ (or the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein) is often seen, but we argue that there should be an entropy for the first equilibration scheme as well. Furthermore, even in the second equilibration scheme, we argue that an $\exp(-i E_i t)$ exists and that this might have an effect on the second entropy which one does not see present in usual calculations which consider energy E_i of a bound state as given value with no fluctuations due to $\exp(-i E_i t)$ included.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in classical statistical mechanics there is one equilibration scheme based on maximization of entropy subject to the constraint of $\sum_i e_i p(i)$. Thus maximization of entropy at a point x governs the probabilities for different kinetic energy values, even in the presence of a potential $V(x)$.

We argue that for a quantum single particle bound state there are two equilibration schemes. The first, based on the built-in probability $\exp(ipx)$, conservation of energy and boundary conditions, fixes the allowed values of total energy, which turn out to be discrete. This first scheme of equilibration has nothing to do with maximization of entropy, it seems, and should be associated with its own entropy. In the literature, one sees $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)a(p)$, where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, used in Shannon's entropy expressions.

Given a discrete set of E_{total} values, one may then have a second equilibration based on maximization of entropy subject to an average energy constraint. This applies to photons being absorbed and emitted and the particle jumping from one E_i to another. We argue, however, that from the first equilibration scheme, there exists the factor $\exp(-iE_i t)$ which should create a kind of temporal entropy which may need to be incorporated with the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e_i/T)$ used for a system jumping from one energy level to another.